

A Solar-Powered, Low-Cost Cargo Delivery Drone

Daniel Makana Raini¹, Kelvin Wainaina Githinji², Dr. Davies Rene Segera³,

¹ Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, UoN, Kenya

² Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, UoN, Kenya

³ Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, UoN, Kenya

Received: ... / Accepted: ...

©The Authors 2024

Abstract / This paper outlines the design and development of a low-cost, solar-powered cargo delivery drone, focused on logistics and humanitarian aid applications in Kenya. The goal is to provide a sustainable and affordable solution for delivery in remote areas, improving logistics efficiency and food distribution in regions affected by poverty and drought. The paper also explores key technological considerations, such as the integration of solar cells to maximize the drone's energy efficiency in various climatic conditions. This paper explores the control of such a drone using a mobile phone via short messages for convenience.

Keywords / Solar-powered drones — Cargo Delivery Drone — Arduino — Mobile phone controlled drone—low-cost drone

1. Introduction

In the recent years, Kenya's need for more efficient and sustainable logistics solutions is on the increase. The demand for environmentally friendly delivery options in the country is propelled by the rapid growth of e-commerce. Some of the challenges Kenya faces with traditional cargo delivery methods, using trucks and vans, include increased carbon emissions, road congestion, high operational costs, and a requirement for better access to rural and remote areas. In response, Kenyan researchers and industry players see unmanned aerial vehicles, or more colloquially known as drones, as a promising alternative method of last-mile delivery for areas where infrastructure development might be minimal.

Battery-powered drones have demonstrated potential in recent years, yet they are often constrained by their finite battery life, leading to limited flight ranges and restricted operational flexibility. Solar-powered UAVs, however, offer an innovative solution by harnessing Kenya's abundant sunlight as a renewable energy source, enabling extended flight durations and reducing dependency on frequent recharging—both crucial factors for delivery efficiency in Kenya's diverse landscapes and remote regions.[7]

This project is aimed at the design of a solar-powered, cost-effective cargo delivery drone with a specific design for Kenya's unique delivery challenges: rural accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and environmental sustainability. This UAV will be powered by solar energy, hence an environmentally friendly solution that can easily be scaled up for logistics companies in Kenya looking to reduce carbon emissions while increasing their reach.

This paper presents the main design considerations, challenges, and technological needs for a feasible solar-powered drone for Kenya. The salient features that will be discussed in this paper include lightweight material selection for efficiency, sophisticated power management techniques, aerodynamic refinement for longer flights, and the integration of solar photovoltaic cells to optimize energy use in accordance with Kenya's geographical and environmental conditions.

Beyond logistics, drone technology does have a lot of prospect for humanitarian needs in several dry, poor, or food-insecure parts of the country. In areas like northern and northeastern Kenya, which are bound to experience protracted droughts, lack of infrastructure, and poor road conditions, access is always going to be very difficult when aid and relief supplies are sent out. These areas often have impassable roads or transportation that is not economically feasible to allow for more traditional methods of delivery.

Solar-powered drones are increasingly becoming an efficient and cost-effective alternative in the delivery of relief food to remote communities. Equipped with the capability of flying over difficult terrain, the UAVs can deliver urgent supplies like food, water, and medical aid rapidly to areas that would otherwise be inaccessible or extremely costly to reach. By relying on solar energy, these drones can offer a sustainable, low-cost solution for food distribution, reducing the environmental impact associated with traditional relief operations.

The objective of the project is to explore a solar-powered UAV as a versatile tool that can address logistics and humanitarian applications, including relief food delivery. The design of the UAV will focus on features relevant to such missions, including the integration of high-

resolution cameras and payload capabilities to transport relief goods with real-time data transmission to coordinate delivery efforts. It will be necessary to ensure that the drone can operate effectively over long distances and through challenging weather conditions, common in Kenya's arid regions, by using lightweight materials, aerodynamic optimization, and efficient power management.

By serving both logistical and humanitarian needs, such a dual-purpose UAV might dramatically improve Kenya's capability for more efficient aid delivery and further sustainable and environmentally friendly technological solutions. Development of such technology could cut down on operational costs and environmental impact of traditional relief operations, thus providing Kenya with a scalable, high-impact solution for addressing both its logistical and humanitarian challenges.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Overview of Drone Technology

2.1.1. Historical Context

The development of drone technology has evolved from its rudimentary beginnings as a military technology to its modern applications in various commercial and consumer sectors. Drones, or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), originated from early 20th-century military experiments. These early machines, whether remote-controlled or autonomous instruments of war, barely resembled today's sophisticated devices. However, their core function of extending human capabilities and reach was already apparent.[16, 12] World War I saw the use of

Transition of Drone Technology from Military to Civilian Use

Fig. 1. Timeline showing the evolution of drone technology from military applications to civilian use, highlighting key milestones including early military UAVs in World War I, Cold War reconnaissance drones, and modern commercial applications like aerial photography and delivery services.

unmanned aerial torpedoes by both the U.S. Navy and

the British Royal Navy. Between the World Wars, militaries experimented with radio-controlled aircraft for target practice. During World War II, both Germany and Great Britain developed remote-controlled aircraft. The Cold War era marked a turning point in drone development, as both the United States and the Soviet Union invested heavily in unmanned reconnaissance aircraft. The 1990s saw the development of the General Atomics MQ-1 Predator, initially used for reconnaissance but later adapted for attack missions. Following 9/11, military drones, such as the MQ-9 Reaper, became integral to U.S. counterterrorism operations.

As regulations relaxed and technology became more accessible, drones transitioned from military to civilian use. The DJI Phantom series brought aerial photography and videography to the masses with affordable and easy-to-operate consumer drones. By 2013, Amazon CEO Jeff Bezos announced plans for Amazon Prime Air, a drone-based delivery service. This period saw increased interest in specialized applications, such as agriculture, where drones could monitor crops and spray pesticides [?].

2.1.2. Technological Advancements

Several key technological advancements have enabled the development of modern drone technology. Miniaturized electronics, robust materials, and better propulsion systems have made drones lighter, more efficient, and more versatile. Advancements in battery life, autonomous navigation, and sensor technology have further enhanced drone capabilities[1, 11]. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning has enabled drones to make independent decisions based on real-time data [1]. Developments in GPS technology and sensor fusion algorithms have enabled precise navigation and autonomous flight. The emergence of First Person View (FPV) systems allows pilots to experience flight from the drone's perspective, leading to new applications in drone racing and immersive filmmaking. Software development kits (SDKs) provide the tools for developers to create custom applications for drones, expanding their potential across various sectors.

2.1.3. Current and Future Challenges

Despite rapid advancements, drone technology still faces several challenges. Limited flight times due to battery constraints remain a significant obstacle [20, 17]. Cybersecurity threats are a growing concern as drones become more connected. Privacy concerns and the ethical implications of drone use in surveillance and military operations require careful consideration [9, 21]. The development of regulations and safety protocols is crucial for the safe integration of drones into airspace. Future developments in drone technology are expected to address these challenges and expand their capabilities further. Researchers are working on making drones

Fig. 2. Comprehensive overview of technological breakthroughs in drone development, including miniaturized electronics, advanced propulsion systems, improved battery technology, AI integration, and enhanced sensor capabilities that have enabled modern drone applications.

smaller, lighter, more efficient, and cheaper. Drones are expected to become more autonomous and capable of operating in swarms. Long-distance drones with vertical takeoff and landing (VTOL) technology are expected to become more widespread. Improved navigation technology, obstacle detection, and 5G integration will enhance drone functionality. The use of solar cells could potentially extend flight times [9].

2.1.4. Current Trends in Drone Technology

Presently, drones are becoming increasingly integrated with artificial intelligence and machine learning, the driving forces behind enabling them to carry out complex tasks autonomously and intelligently. AI algorithms allow self-decision-making, adaptive behavior, and advanced maneuverability. Applications of AI in drones include computer vision for autonomous navigation, deep learning for object detection and tracking, and reinforcement learning for optimal path planning. AI is also applied to predict the maintenance of the components of drones by utilizing neural networks to estimate any failure that may occur.

Beyond Visual Line of Sight operations, enabling the drone to fly beyond the range of the pilot’s vision, is another area of major development. BVLOS operations will be able to greatly extend both the range and utility of drone applications, becoming suitable for long-range infrastructure inspections, real-time environmental monitoring, and advanced search and rescue. Major technological challenges to BVLOS will involve GPS accuracy, more advanced obstacle detection and avoidance systems, and the reliability of the data transmitted over long distance. Regulatory frameworks are changing to allow safe BVLOS operations and an-

swer concerns on airspace integration, privacy, and security. The enhancement in sensor technology is upgrading drones’ functionalities in various applications. Drones will come equipped with a suite of sensors, including high-resolution cameras, thermal imaging systems, LiDAR, and radar, to capture data from many dimensions. Sensors enable the use of these devices for wildlife observation, habitat analysis, structure inspection, and search and rescue. Advanced sensors are also crucial to the BVLOS operations as it helps the drone to move safely beyond the line of sight of the operator.

These SDKs essentially give developers the tools to create their own solutions for specialized tasks. Such software packages have flexibility beyond the limitations imposed by pre-installed software, thus allowing developers to tailor drones for specific research, business, or industrial applications. In summary, SDKs democratize drone technology, making innovation and creating tailored solutions possible for a wide range of needs.

Swarm technology, wherein a number of drones coordinate with each other, opens a new perspective in the possible use of drones. The swarm of drones will increase efficiency in searching, rescuing, monitoring of the environment, and large-scale data gathering. Challenges in Swarm Technology: Development of complicated algorithms to control the swarm and overcoming regulatory hurdles while operating several drones in civil airspace.

In the future, drones will increasingly be fitted with solar technology to meet the limitation of battery life and permit longer flights. Solar-powered drones are being researched for a number of purposes, including persistent surveillance, long-range data acquisition, and high-altitude atmospheric research. The Airbus Zephyr is one such solar-powered drone that set a world record in the long endurance of flying, exemplifying what could be possible with such technology.

Advancements in Drone Technology

Fig. 3. Detailed visualization of current and emerging trends in drone technology, showcasing the integration of artificial intelligence, beyond visual line of sight (BVLOS) operations, advanced sensor systems, and the development of autonomous capabilities for various applications.

2.1.5. How Drones Are Currently Being Used in Logistics, Especially For Last-Mile Delivery

The biggest impact drones are having on logistics today is in warehousing and inventory. Drones make the processes of a warehouse more efficient and cost-effective by automating inventory checks. With cameras and scanning technology, drones can execute an inventory audit much faster than methods of old. They scan the barcodes placed at higher shelves without any use of ladders by the workers or heavy machinery. The data received is transmitted to the warehouse management system, which will present real-time inventory levels to identify discrepancies. With their ability to fly up and down narrow aisles and into tight spaces, drones facilitate much more efficient and highly accurate inventory management. Drones save a lot in labor costs while eliminating safety risks from inventory checks, especially in very large warehouses with high-bay racking systems. Drones could be used in warehouses for surveillance and security, patrolling, intruder detection, and live video feeds to security personnel.

Drones have been tested and rolled out for last-mile delivery but are still being confined due to regulatory hurdles and logistic challenges. Nowadays, drones are applied in cases of specialized deliveries for small, high-value items such as medicines and blood donations. Many times, these deliveries have unreachable areas by classic transport modes as their target. Wide-ranging regulation in airspace, safety, and privacy inhibits wide-ranging diffusion for last-mile delivery. But aside from these, there are several challenges on the logistics side of drone delivery, like disposition, the landing infrastructure in city environments, generally small payload capacity for most drones, and theft of packages. However, notwithstanding such challenges, the application of drones would grow in deliveries and other transport functions given the sustained pressure that land supply chains undergo. And to that view, massive tech development lies in heavy-duty drones to autonomous navigation, making more and wide-ranging uses in future times a promise.

A number of companies are already putting drones into logistics. DHL has been testing drone delivery of medicines to a hospital in Bonn, Germany, and has implemented drone surveillance in South America to improve security and reduce patrol time. Amazon is pioneering drone-based delivery services, though their implementation faces regulatory and logistical hurdles. Zipline provides emergency package delivery, mainly in less developed regions.

2.1.6. Key Takeaways

Warehousing and inventory management are the most significant areas of impact that drones are currently creating within logistics. Last-mile delivery, however, is still in the infancy stage but is perceived to have huge potential in the future. Advances in technology and

changes in regulations are going to be important determinants in the future of logistics with the use of drones.

2.2. Solar-Powered Drones

2.2.1. Advantages of Integration of Solar Power into UAVs

Several of the positive benefits concerning the use of solar power with UAVs are long flight and range times, sustainability, and lower operational costs [17, 7]. The traditional battery-powered drones have very limited flight times, which has a direct consequence on their operational range and task difficulty. Solar power, therefore, becomes one solution that, while the UAV is in flight, can continue to supply energy from the sun, greatly extending its operational possibilities. The solar panels serve to constantly replenish the UAV's energy while it is flying; hence, longer mission times, persistent surveillance, and extending its operational reach are possible. Solar-powered UAVs reduce the frequency of returns to base for recharging, reducing downtime and thereby enhancing operational efficiency. This advantage is particularly valuable in scenarios where ground-based charging is problematic, such as remote areas, disaster zones, or maritime environments.

Solar-powered UAVs, therefore, are considered to be more environmentally friendly, considering the latest trend towards sustainable aviation. Solar energy is basically renewable and clean, offering a more suitable alternative to fossil fuels such that the environmental impact due to the drone operation can be minimized. Equally, with the help of solar energy, UAVs can operate with a hugely reduced carbon footprint to ensure a greener aviation industry.

Comparing UAV Energy Sources: Solar vs. Battery

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis of traditional battery-powered drones versus solar-powered UAVs, illustrating the significant advantages in terms of extended flight duration, reduced operational costs, and enhanced sustainability through continuous solar energy harvesting.

In general, powering UAVs with solar means long-term cost-effectiveness. Solar energy reduces and, in most cases, eliminates the demand to draw electricity from the grid to charge UAVs and is likely to reduce energy costs for operators. Solar panels require little maintenance compared to combustion engines or battery systems.

2.2.2. Examples of Solar-Powered UAVs

Several companies are developing and deploying solar-powered UAVs. Sunbirds, a French company, designs and sells solar-powered UAVs that can operate for over 10 hours under ideal conditions. Their drones are used for mapping, aerial photography, and surveillance. AeroVironment is developing High-Altitude Long-Endurance (HALE) solar drones in partnership with SoftBank for commercial applications. Airbus designed the Zephyr, a solar-powered drone under test in the US Army, that could operate in the stratosphere for very long periods. XSun has designed a fully solar-powered UAV for missions such as mapping, topography missions, and infrastructure inspection. The solar panels increase its flight time up to 12 hours.

While the technology is still in its development phase, solar-powered UAV has immense potential for various industries. With more research and development in this field, even more innovative applications and technological advancements will be discovered that could enhance the capability of solar-powered UAVs even further and help towards a more sustainable future.

2.3. Applications in Logistics

2.3.1. Applications of Drones in Humanitarian Aid and Emergency Response

Drones are being used to provide humanitarian aid and assist in emergency response situations. They deliver medical supplies such as medicine, trauma kits, and even organs for transplantation to remote or disaster-stricken areas that are hard to reach using traditional methods. Drones deliver these life-saving supplies much faster than conventional methods. For example, drones deliver defibrillators to patients experiencing cardiac arrest 32% faster in urban areas and 93% faster in rural areas. Drones also transport food, packages, and other essential goods in emergency situations, especially in hard-to-reach areas. In search and rescue operations, drones search for injured people, assess the damage of a disaster zone, and guide rescue teams. Drones operate effectively even when the extent of the disaster is unknown and in harsh conditions. Drones with thermal imaging cameras are particularly useful for locating missing people at night or in conditions with low visibility. For example, drones with thermal cameras detect poachers in Kenya and are used in avalanche rescue efforts. Drones also support emergency response teams

such as the fire brigade and police. They use thermal cameras to detect gas leaks, allowing emergency teams to intervene quickly and safely. Additionally, drones establish communication networks for emergency response teams. The increasing affordability and accessibility of drones make them valuable tools for humanitarian purposes[21]

2.3.2. The Function of Drones in Border Surveillance and Security

The functions of drones extend to border surveillance and security. Equipped with high-definition cameras and advanced sensors, drones are an economical and effective means of conducting surveillance across vast expanses of borders. They facilitate the real-time situational awareness of border patrol agents by helping them detect illegal crossings and other smuggling activities, in addition to other security threats. Drones collect data on possible dangers, suspicious activities, and geographical features around borders. It enhances border security strategies and resource deployment. In the event of a security breach or any other emergency, drones are rapidly mobilized to inspect the scene of the crime, track suspects, and lead ground units to the site. Their agility and speed turn them into irreplaceable tools in rapid response operations. Drones reduce border surveillance costs by a significant margin compared to traditional methods such as ground patrols or manned aircraft. They require less manpower, have lower operational costs, and can cover larger areas more efficiently. Drones patrol dangerous or difficult-to-access areas along borders, reducing the risk to human patrol agents. They also operate in hazardous environments, like extreme temperatures or areas with chemical spills. The visible presence of drones acts to deter these activities, making it clear to potential border crossers or smugglers that this is not a secure environment.

Certain technologies enhance the effectiveness of drones in border security. Thermal cameras enable the drones to detect heat signatures, thus enabling the locating of people or vehicles in the dark or in heavy foliage. This enables the detection of night border crossings. Long-endurance flying, especially solar-powered drones, can provide site persistence for long periods. That means borderline areas can be continuously monitored to avoid any activity going undetected. Equipped with an array of sensors, including radar, LiDAR, and multispectral cameras, drones can detect movement, identify objects, and gather detailed information about the terrain for a comprehensive picture of the border environment. Some of the uses of drones in the military for border security include basic surveillance, reconnaissance, and intelligence gathering. Similar applications are relevant to border security in a military context.

3. System Design and Architecture

Design and architecture represent the key to attaining the exacting standards in performance, efficiency, and operational reliability for a solar-powered cargo delivery drone [15, 19]. This section highlights the fundamental hardware-software elements to be built into the aircraft, especially focusing on solar power integration with a view to achieving enhanced energy efficiency and an extended flight range. The system design is approached holistically, considering both the mechanical and electrical subsystems, as well as the software that governs flight control, communication, and power management.

Hardware architecture involves the selection of the flight platform, propulsion system, power distribution, and energy management components, while software architecture focuses on the development of control algorithms, telemetry data processing, and integration with mobile applications for remote operation. Particular attention is paid to the fact that the solar power system should interact seamlessly with the drone's other subsystems for the purpose of optimum energy use, flight duration, and payload capacity. We consider these design elements in an effort to create a functional, cost-effective, scalable solution for last-mile cargo delivery.

3.1. Hardware Design

The primary objective dictated by the problem question is to design a solar-powered cargo delivery drone. In this paper, we take a cargo limit of not less than one kilogram. From this, we can obtain the components to make the build using the following design process.

The requirements for the drone are as follows:

3.1.1. The Platform

Given the goal of designing and implementing a long range and endurance drone capable of carrying substantial weight, in this case one kilogram, we decided to opt for a quad-rotor configuration. This decision was to take full advantage of the control and maneuverability of the drone once loaded. This would do away with the need of a launch rail or runway as is for fixed wing configurations. The number of rotors was decided to save on cost and power usage. Due to the spacing of a quad-rotor configuration the size of the propellers could be picked with less restrictions. It is less congested than other higher order multi-rotor configurations. The space is necessary for placing solar panels. This would hence increase overall efficiency compared to other configurations. It also calls for a simplified build. Although hex copters excel in speed and stability, our main objective was endurance and efficiency provided by the quad-rotor configuration.[?] [16]

3.1.2. The Flight Controller

The drone control unit is based on the Arduino Mega 2560 mini pro board. This is a powerful board offering a generous number of input and output pins. Listing some of its features:

- an ATmega 2560(16 MHz) microcontroller
- 54 Digital I/O pins
- 15 PWM pins

These features are to be leveraged in the design of the Electronic Speed Controller (ESC) units, Battery Management System (BMS) and Power Delivery Board (PDB). The controller performance will be crucial for handling and processing sensor data for state observation and state estimation. This eliminates the use of individual microprocessors for the above stated use cases, a reduction in cost and power consumption.[15] The Mega 2560 will be programmed in C. The choice of language was to enhance processing speed and to address the mission critical agenda. This combination produces a powerful, cost effective, secure yet fast platform that addresses the cost effectiveness of the drone.

3.1.3. The Motors

Given a payload of one kilogram and the weight of the entire drone as two kilograms, the following estimations were made. Using a 2:1 thrust-to-weight ratio, the motors can lift the drone at half throttle, the total thrust required from the motor would be that of six kilograms.

$$\text{Thrust per motor} = \frac{\text{Total Thrust Required}}{\text{Number of Motors}}$$

Substituting the values:

$$\text{Thrust per motor} = \frac{6 \text{ kg}}{4} = 1.5 \text{ kg/motor}$$

We therefore recommend brush less (BLCD) motors with a thrust of 1.5 kg to 2 kg thrust. BLCD motors are three phase motors that are quite efficient compared with brushed motors and can reliably provide their rated thrust once coupled up with their recommended propellers. They however draw a lot of current and have high voltage ratings. Selecting a good battery and ESC is therefore crucial in order to get the desired performance.[8]

3.1.4. The Electronic Speed Controller (ESC)

Using BLCD motors creates a requirement of designing ESC for each motor. This unit controls the switching of the power in the coils of the motor. This is done sequentially enabling the motor to start and run uninterrupted. The motors draw a lot of current and high voltages. The rating of these voltages should be considered. A margin of the ratings is added to account for over current due to

heating as the ESC mainly comprises of fast switching MOSFETs.

In this paper, we will design an ESC with a 30A current rating and a 20V voltage rating. The processing power for controlling the switching will be tapped from the Mega 2560, utilizing one of its cores.

3.1.5. The Battery

The specifications for motor clearly give a range of batteries to be incorporated in this build. Given a limit of not less than 4S battery for the operation of the motor and observing the weight limit for this design to hold, two Lithium ion batteries are chosen one to service the motors and another the electronics on board. They will averagely weigh 300g leaving a margin for the electronics and chassis. The battery voltage and current ratings will be in line with the motor chosen. Lithium ion batteries were chosen because of their high charge and discharge cycles and efficiency.

3.1.6. The Battery Management System (BMS)

The battery management system is necessary in this build to manage the amount of power entering the battery pack. We are proposing a three port system, one that charges the battery from the solar panels. The BMS monitors this operation such that when the battery is full, power from the solar is diverted to the Power Delivery Board. This power is then fed to the electronics to drive operations directly. The BMS offers protection to the battery from surges in power from the solar panels ensuring long battery life. Any processing power will utilize the Arduino Mega 2560.

3.1.7. The Power Distribution Board (PDU)

This unit is proposed to handle power from the battery and solar panels to the electronics on board. This is to provide step up or step down where necessary as well as offering protection to the electronics on board. This unit is proposed to provide steady currents and voltages, clean power, at all times.

A KILL switch is to be incorporated. This isolates all electronics on board from the power providing a safety feature in case of any inconvenience.

3.1.8. Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU)

A variety of sensors will be incorporated in for flight control. Data from these sensors will be used for state observation and state estimation. These will form the Inertial Measurement unit also referred to as the Attitude and Heading Reference System. Once data is collected from the sensors the Mega 2560 processes this

data giving corrections for noise and vibrations. This processed data will be used for controlling the drone instead of using raw data. Among these sensors includes an accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer and a barometer. The accelerometer measures the change in velocity in time. It will be useful for telling the speed of the cargo drone. The gyroscope and magnetometer will provide data useful for the cargo drone positioning and orientation. The Barometer will be crucial for determining the height of the drone.[2][18]

3.1.9. Radio Receiver and Transmitter

We propose using the GSM SIM800L module for communication with the drone. This is to take full advantage of the long range using sms. This set up offers reliability, range and ensures smooth flight data transmission at low power.[3]

3.1.10. Solar Panels

The solar panels to be incorporated are not only intended to recharge the battery pack, but also to relieve the battery pack of one if not all functions. We propose to run the electronics purely on solar power. Due to the space limit, the solar panels have to have high efficiency in order to accomplish this.[17]

3.1.11. Basic Quad-rotor Motion

There are various configurations for a quad-rotor, the X , $+$ and H configuration. In all configurations, adjusting the angular velocity of the rotors controls the direction and orientation of the drone. The rotors do not rotate in one direction, this is due to movement caused by inertia effect. To mitigate this, adjacent rotors are driven in opposite directions while opposite rotors have rotation in the same direction.[10]

The motion of a quad-rotor can be modeled in 2D space. Operation of a quad-rotor utilizes the control of motor angular velocity to achieve a resultant horizontal motion. The angular velocities of the motors can be adjusted to achieve various operations.

Among them is **hovering or throttle** operation. In this operation, all motors have equal angular velocity. A vertical force is hence induced. This operation moves the drone up/down or maintains vertical position (altitude), hovering.

The **yaw** operation is the counterclockwise rotation of a about the z-axis. This translates to the right/left rotation of the drone about the z-axis. This can be achieved by increasing the angular velocity of opposite rotors.

The **pitch** operation is the counterclockwise rotation of b about the y-axis. This translates to the up/down tilting of the drone about the y-axis. This can be achieved

by increasing the angular velocity of adjacent rotors of the drone bisected by the y-axis.

The **roll** operation is the counterclockwise rotation of c about the x-axis. This translates to the up/down tilting of the drone about the x-axis. This can be achieved by increasing the angular velocity of adjacent rotors of the drone bisected by the x-axis.[11]

3.1.12. Modeling A Quad-rotor

The rotation matrices for the 3D axis representing the yaw, pitch and roll can be identified as ;

The yaw rotation matrix:

$$A_z(a) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(a) & -\sin(a) & 0 \\ \sin(a) & \cos(a) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The pitch rotation matrix:

$$A_y(y) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(b) & 0 & \sin(b) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(b) & 0 & \cos(b) \end{bmatrix}$$

The roll rotation matrix:

$$A_x(c) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(c) & -\sin(c) \\ 0 & \sin(c) & \cos(c) \end{bmatrix}$$

These rotations can be used to place a 3D body in any orientation. A single rotation matrix can be obtained by multiplying the yaw ,pitch and roll rotation matrices to obtain:

$$A(a, b, c) = A_z(a)A_y(b)A_x(c)$$

⇒

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos(a)\cos(b)\cos(c) & \cos(a)\sin(b)\sin(c) - \sin(a)\cos(c) & \cos(a)\sin(b)\cos(c) + \sin(a)\sin(c) \\ \sin(a)\cos(b)\cos(c) & \sin(a)\sin(b)\sin(c) + \cos(a)\cos(c) & \sin(a)\sin(b)\cos(c) - \cos(a)\sin(c) \\ -\sin(b) & \cos(b)\sin(c) & \cos(b)\cos(c) \end{bmatrix}$$

[19][13]

3.2. Software Design

The system software forms an integral layer that allows easy communication between the drone and its controller. It aims to provide the best performance while maintaining simplicity in user interaction. It includes flight control, telemetry processing, and communication protocols for both autonomous and manual operating modes. This section will provide a detailed analysis of the system software architecture, communication modules, and control algorithms that can be utilized in the system.[12]

3.2.1. Software Architecture

The application is built on a robust foundation using modern Android development practices, specifically implementing the Model-View-ViewModel (MVVM) architecture pattern. This architectural choice ensures a clear separation of concerns, making the system more maintainable and scalable. The application is developed using Kotlin as the primary programming language, leveraging Jetpack Compose for modern UI development and Material 3 design system for a consistent user experience.

The architecture is structured into several key modules, each serving a specific purpose. The Flight Control Module is responsible for real-time stabilization and drone navigation. This module communicates with various sensors, including the Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and Global Positioning System (GPS), to determine necessary adjustments to the drone's motors. The Communication Module manages the data link between the ground station and the drone, utilizing multiple protocols including MQTT (implemented through Eclipse Paho), Retrofit for network operations, and Socket.IO for real-time communication.

The Power Management Module monitors the solar panel and battery energy levels, ensuring efficient operation and providing alerts for low power situations. The Data Logging Module records telemetry data such as altitude, velocity, and battery levels for later analysis and diagnostics. Finally, the User Interface Module handles communication with the mobile application, displaying real-time telemetry data and processing user commands.

3.2.2. Communication Protocols

The system utilizes a proprietary communication protocol with low latency and high data integrity, ensuring efficient and reliable communication. This protocol includes not only the transmission of commands that encapsulate instructions coming from the mobile application, like take-off, landing, and waypoint navigation, but also telemetry supporting the streaming of real-time data to the control interface. It also implements error handling in the form of checksums and acknowledgment packets, which are used to detect and correct transmission errors.

3.2.3. Selection of Communication Protocol

The selection of the proper communication protocol is critical for efficient and reliable data transfer between the drone and its control interface. According to operational requirements, three different communication technologies are evaluated. With low power consumption, Bluetooth performs more appropriately in indoor or constrained operating scenarios. Wi-Fi provides high data

Fig. 5. Detailed system architecture diagram illustrating the integration of key software modules including flight control systems, communication protocols, power management, and data logging components, showing their interconnections and data flow patterns.

Which communication protocol should be used for transmitting commands to the drone?

Bluetooth
Suitable for short-range communication with low power consumption.

Wi-Fi
Ideal for high data rate transmission over longer distances.

GSM/GPRS
Best for global coverage and remote area operation.

Fig. 6. Each protocol can be categorized in terms of its range, data rate capabilities, and suitability for certain environments

rates suitable for medium- to long-range data transmissions and finds the perfect balance between range and throughput. The GSM/GPRS enables good global coverage to be used in the most remote area operations

when the other conventional short-range communication protocols are ineffective or even impracticable.

Ultimately, Wi-Fi can be selected for the drone application because it represents the best trade-off between range and throughput, enabling communication at intermediate distances.

3.2.4. Telemetry Data Processing

The drone telemetry system is designed to transmit critical flight information to the control interface for monitoring and analysis purposes. This includes the transmission of telemetry information where the drone sends real-time metrics, such as altitude, speed, and battery status, to the mobile application. The received telemetry data is parsed and processed for presentation in a user-friendly format on the control interface. The modular design of the software architecture ensures flexibility in adding new telemetry parameters without affecting the core system.

Fig. 7. Comprehensive telemetry data processing pipeline showing that sensor data is collected, filtered, processed, and transmitted to the control interface, including data validation, error correction, and real-time monitoring capabilities.

3.2.5. Information Transmission and Directives Implementation

The communication flow in the system depicts the different stages that take place from user input to the execution of commands on the drone. First, commands are initiated through the mobile application interface, which includes instructions for flight control or navigation. These commands are then encoded into a suitable format for transmission. The encoded commands are then transmitted wirelessly to the drone using the designated communication protocol.

The Arduino-based control system of the drone interprets these commands and takes the necessary actions, such as changes in motor speeds or moving to a given waypoint. This efficient process ensures the lowest latency possible and that the commands are executed effectively to enhance the overall reliability of the system.

Fig. 8. Multi-layered communication protocol architecture showing the integration of different communication technologies (Wi-Fi, GSM, MQTT) and the flow of data.

3.2.6. Control Algorithms

Advanced algorithms, part of the software of the drone, are developed to increase flight stability and accuracy. The PID control algorithm is applied to stabilize the attitude of the drone and maintain its altitude. The waypoint navigation algorithm implements autonomous navigation, which directs the drone from one waypoint to another based on GPS coordinates. Lastly, power optimization algorithms help regulate power consumption based on available solar energy and battery levels to maximize flying times.

3.2.7. Integration with Mobile Application

The Kotlin-developed mobile application serves as an interface through which the user operates the drone. The application offers a real-time controller displaying buttons and sliders for manual movement control. Further, the application supports mission planning, allowing users to set waypoints and plan delivery routes. The application is also designed with telemetry monitoring, showing in real time the status of the battery, speed, and GPS location.

4. Implementation

4.1. Software Development

The development and actual specifications of the system software development are multifaceted. The application is built with specific technical requirements in mind, targeting Android SDK version 34 as the minimum requirement, with compilation against SDK version 35. The application is developed using Java 11, ensuring compatibility with modern Android devices while maintaining performance.

Security is a paramount concern in the development process. The application implements robust security measures, including MQTT authentication with username and password protection, secure communication protocols, and data encryption for sensitive information. Special attention is paid to permission handling for SMS and location services, ensuring user privacy and system security.

Performance optimization is achieved through careful consideration of memory management, battery usage, and network efficiency. The real-time data processing system is optimized to handle continuous streams of

telemetry data, while the map rendering system (implemented using OpenStreetMap through the OSMDroid library) is tuned for smooth performance.

The testing strategy is comprehensive, covering unit testing for core functionality, UI testing using Espresso, integration testing for communication modules, and performance testing for real-time operations. Error scenarios are thoroughly tested to ensure system reliability under various conditions.

4.2. Mobile Application Development

4.2.1. Architecture and Framework

The mobile application is built using Kotlin and Jetpack Compose, following the MVVM (Model-View-ViewModel) architecture pattern. This serves benefits such as having a clear separation of concerns between UI (User Interface), business logic, and data layers. Also it gives that reactive programming since we want to handle real-time updates.

Fig. 9. User interface layout of the mobile application featuring an OpenStreetMap integration for drone tracking, control buttons for takeoff and landing operations, and real-time telemetry display showing speed, altitude, and battery status.

4.2.2. Key Components

UI layer

The User Interface layout for the page has a 100 percent Open Street Map(Map Section) from the osmdroid library with overlays of the controls section and the telemetry section. The map section displays the drone location on the map using a blue png marker of the drone's location actively centred and repositions with a long time detection of the marker not being centred. The controls section has buttons of 'takeoff' and 'land' whose functionalities we will look at deeply in the sections that follow. The controls section basically sends commands to the drone upon clicking either one for target operations and control of the drone. The telemetry section displays real-time drone data such as speed, altitude and battery levels.

Fig. 10. Mobile application chat feature illustrating some of the commands illustrating the on-command uses of this feature

The layout also incorporates other pages such as the Settings screen, the View logs screen, the chat screen, the splash screen and a currently redundant MQTT Debug console. The settings screen contains editable details of the broker URL, the username and password for the purpose of MQTT configuration. The view logs screen tails the connections and their timestamps. For instance connections via SMS, connections with the web app server, connections with the broker among several other connections with their recent feedback statuses are logged here for the time the mobile app is running. The details of whether the app is receiving data and what kind of data are also listed in the View Logs screen. The

chat screen is where the user, through the drone application can chat with the drone through specific commands. Commands such as 'hello' which is a conversation starter. 'Help' command makes the drone to list drop-down of the menu of commands with their functionalities. The 'status' command gets the drone status in terms of speed, altitude and battery levels. The 'position' command gets the current position of the drone in terms of latitudes and longitudes. The 'rtl' command gets the drone to return to its launch position.

Business Logic Layer

This serves in acting as the brain of this mobile application, orchestrating the interactions between the UI layer and the data storage or retrieval mechanisms. Its primary role is to implement the core protocols or rules for governing the behavior of this application.

The DroneViewModel is responsible for holding and managing UI-related data in a lifecycle-conscious way. For our case, it maintains the current state of the drone, that is, its GPS coordinates, battery level, altitude, speed, error logic among many other operational parameters. The DroneViewModel also manages the state of the application's UI elements that depend on drone data. For example, when it comes to enabling and/or disabling control buttons based on the connection status, updating telemetry or displaying warnings. The DroneView Model acts as an intermediary where it receives user input from the UI layer and translates it into actions for the Data Layer and translates it into actions for the Data Layer or direct commands to the drone. Conversely, it also receives data updates from the Data Layer(new telemetry for example) and prepares them for display by the UI layer.

Command-processing and validation is a significant sub-component that ensures safe and correct drone operation. It handles receiving user commands('takeoff', 'land', 'return to home' among others), validating commands and translating commands.

Telemetry data processing is also handled here in this layer. Here is where the raw telemetry data is received, data is parsed and interpreted, it is filtered and smoothed, if there are calculations they are performed, and the application state is also updated.

The connection management component handles the life cycle and stability of the communication link between the mobile app and the drone. Some of its responsibilities include establishing connections, monitoring the communication status, handling disconnections and managing multiple connections.

Finally, handling of errors and recovery from such errors is done here. The error detections, logging those errors, providing the user with feedback and implementing recovery strategies are some of the focus areas in this part.

Much of the documentation of the code is available and

elaborate in the git hub repository.

Fig. 11. Business logic layer implementation diagram showing the interaction between the DroneViewModel, command processing system, telemetry data handling, and connection management components, with emphasis on error handling and state management thus showing the logs for different simulated states.

that we are to send to the drone are that of 'takeoff' and 'land'; and it is set to receive data on speed, altitude and battery level; permissions were added in the code for sending and receiving SMS. A utility class for this service was also set up. We modified the onclick protocol for the takeoff and land commands relevantly. Also we set up the code for updating the user interface once the data is received.

4.2.5. Simulated Telemetry

The received telemetry(speed, battery, altitude levels) for checking that both application endpoints could receive data were simulated and that the following data could be sent from the python script(also attached in the github repository) and received in the server after which it could be sent to the mobile application and to the web application and displayed there. Here is the sampled telemetry that was generated and simulated from the python code script:

4.2.3. Communication Implementation

The mobile app implements a dual-communication strategy. It has a primary communication and a fallback communication. The primary communication is Message Queuing Telemetry Transport(MQTT). The fallback communication is Short Message Service(SMS).

MQTT offers real-time bidirectional communication. It is a topic-based message routing service. It serves automatic reconnection handling and also message queuing for offline operation.

SMS as the fallback communication is purely GSM-based for command encoding and/or decoding. It also serves to give an automatic fallback mechanism. Over SMS, it serves for error detection and correction

4.2.4. Global System for Mobile communications(GSM)

There are several GSM protocols such as SMS, TCP/IP, MQTT. We used the Short Message Service(SMS) because it allows for connection even in remote or reserved areas without failures. Given the accepted commands

Table 1. Complete timeline of simulated drone telemetry data

Time	Battery (%)	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Speed (m/s)	Status Message
12:00:14	36	-1.27973	36.81626	114.0	1.4	GPS confirmed
12:00:16	32	-1.27969	36.81630	116.0	1.6	Payload check
12:00:18	32	-1.27965	36.81634	118.0	1.8	Auto-pilot engaged
12:00:20	32	-1.27961	36.81638	120.0	2.0	Speed increasing
12:00:22	32	-1.27957	36.81642	122.0	2.2	Data streaming
12:00:24	32	-1.27953	36.81646	124.0	2.4	Altitude hold
12:00:26	28	-1.27951	36.81648	125.0	2.5	Approaching waypoint
12:00:28	28	-1.27949	36.81650	126.0	2.6	Sensor check
12:00:30	28	-1.27947	36.81652	127.0	2.7	Systems nominal
12:00:32	28	-1.27945	36.81654	128.0	2.8	Battery warning
12:00:34	28	-1.27943	36.81656	129.0	2.9	Speed adjustment
12:00:36	28	-1.27941	36.81658	130.0	3.0	New flight pattern
12:00:38	28	-1.27939	36.81660	131.0	3.1	Course update
12:00:40	28	-1.27937	36.81662	132.0	3.2	Telemetry stable
12:00:42	28	-1.27935	36.81664	133.0	3.3	Wind detected
12:00:44	28	-1.27933	36.81666	134.0	3.4	Compensation active
12:00:46	24	-1.27931	36.81668	135.0	3.5	Accelerating
12:00:48	24	-1.27929	36.81670	136.0	3.6	Systems normal
12:00:50	24	-1.27927	36.81672	137.0	3.7	Camera active
12:00:52	24	-1.27925	36.81674	138.0	3.8	Data recording
12:00:54	24	-1.27923	36.81676	139.0	3.9	Telemetry stable
12:00:56	24	-1.27921	36.81678	140.0	4.0	Stable ascent
12:00:58	24	-1.27919	36.81680	141.0	4.1	Systems check
12:01:00	24	-1.27917	36.81682	142.0	4.2	Normal operation
12:01:02	24	-1.27915	36.81684	143.0	4.3	GPS confirmed
12:01:04	24	-1.27913	36.81686	144.0	4.4	Waypoint approach
12:01:06	20	-1.27911	36.81688	145.0	4.5	Mid-flight phase
12:01:48	20	-1.27909	36.81690	146.0	4.6	Battery warning
12:01:50	20	-1.27907	36.81692	147.0	4.7	Systems nominal
12:01:52	20	-1.27905	36.81694	148.0	4.8	Speed adjustment
12:01:54	20	-1.27903	36.81696	149.0	4.9	Altitude hold
12:01:56	20	-1.27901	36.81698	150.0	5.0	Maintaining altitude
12:01:58	20	-1.27899	36.81700	151.0	5.1	Telemetry stable
12:02:00	20	-1.27897	36.81702	152.0	5.2	Camera recording
12:02:02	20	-1.27895	36.81704	153.0	5.3	Systems check
12:02:04	20	-1.27893	36.81706	154.0	5.4	Normal operation
12:02:06	16	-1.27891	36.81708	155.0	5.5	Course adjustment
12:02:08	16	-1.27889	36.81710	156.0	5.6	Battery critical
12:02:10	16	-1.27887	36.81712	157.0	5.7	Return initiated
12:02:12	16	-1.27885	36.81714	158.0	5.8	Descending
12:02:14	16	-1.27883	36.81716	159.0	5.9	Speed reduction
12:02:16	12	-1.27881	36.81718	50.0	8.0	EMERGENCY RETURN
12:02:18	12	-1.27879	36.81720	45.0	7.5	Rapid descent
12:02:20	12	-1.27877	36.81722	40.0	7.0	Landing sequence
12:02:22	12	-1.27875	36.81724	35.0	6.5	Approach phase
12:02:24	12	-1.27873	36.81726	30.0	6.0	Final descent
12:02:26	12	-1.27871	36.81728	25.0	5.5	Landing zone confirm
12:02:28	8	-1.27869	36.81730	20.0	5.0	Altitude critical
12:02:30	8	-1.27867	36.81732	15.0	4.5	Final approach

4.3. Web Application Development

The web application component of the drone control system was developed using Node.js along with the Express.js frameworks. The web application serves as a management and monitoring interface. It has all the same qualities of the mobile application save for control operations on the drone. Primarily, it supplies open access for monitoring to the drone via the web.

4.3.1. Frontend Implementation

The dashboard provides for real-time drone status monitoring. It has a section for visualizing telemetry data of speed, altitude, battery level and GPS coordinates. It also offers for the user management of such data through means of planning and such like things. Data visualization is also provided for whereby there is an interactive map, real-time analysis and system health monitoring. The user interface is also fitted in a responsive design for role-based access control. At the same time, it offers for error handling and notifications.

4.3.2. Backend Implementation

The web application backend provides API services since it offers for RESTful endpoints, WebSocket connections and all authentication and authorization as needed. Database operations of analytics, caching and synchronization are handled in the backend

4.3.3. Server Architecture

The server architecture enabled real-time data transfer through the addition of WebSocket, Socket.IO, and MQTT protocols. These layers of communication enabled seamless communication between the drone, server, and client applications. Specifically, the WebSocket support offered continuous bidirectional communication with low-latency data transfer, while the integration of Socket.IO handled automatic reconnections and connection reliability. In addition, the MQTT protocol was configured to enable connection to the HiveMQ cloud broker for lightweight publish-subscribe-based communication between the drone and external systems. The entire communication protocol setup was augmented with extensive error handling protocols, connection retry, quality-of-service levels, and automatic reconnection schemes to prevent data loss and continuous operation.

The system also had to retain the data and have historical analysis capabilities, which were achieved by integrating a MongoDB database. MongoDB's flexibility in storing high amounts of information made it an ideal choice for telemetry data storage, including GPS coordinates, altitude, battery level, flight status, and sensor data output. The database connection was managed

using Mongoose, a Node.js and MongoDB Object Data Modeling library, to allow for structured data management, schema validation, and optimal querying mechanisms. The schema modeling appropriately grouped various telemetry data points for real-time monitoring and historical trend analysis.

The real-time system of communication consisted of multiple layers, each of which ensured efficiency and reliability. A single-task WebSocket server was implemented for the clients to interact directly with the servers for instantaneous response time. Socket.IO, on the other hand, was used to manage real-time updates of telemetry to ensure connection resilience under network fluctuations. An MQTT client was also implemented to be linked with the HiveMQ cloud broker to enable distributed messaging from the drone to backend services. The use of strong error handling capabilities ensured fault tolerance, smooth connection management, and system failure robustness.

The data handling system was structured according to RESTful API endpoints, with clear descriptions of the interaction interfaces. These included a telemetry endpoint to accept drone inputs, a control endpoint to send operational commands, and a historical data extraction endpoint to examine previous flight and performance history. Historical data retrieval system had a feature of advanced aggregation mechanism, allowing time-based data analysis at periodic intervals like hourly, daily, and minute-level report. This offered a more comprehensive review of trends in drone performance and working efficiency.

4.3.4. Security Implementation

Security was of utmost importance during the system's development, aiming at maintaining data integrity and unauthorized access protection. Various security features were incorporated, ranging from CORS protection against malicious cross-origin requests to SSL/TLS encryption of MQTT connections for secure communication and role-based access control systems for controlling access to privileged system operations. Further, sensitive configuration information was protected securely by using environment variables in accordance with industry standards for protecting data.

Data visualization support infrastructure was designed to facilitate seamless integration with frontend visualization software to allow real-time and intuitive monitoring of drones. Graph-oriented real-time visualizations, flight path view, and telemetry analysis dashboards were facilitated through data structured formats. The aggregation framework allowed for dynamic time-based visualizations in order to support users to review the trends in the performance of drones through various visualization techniques such as trend graphs, heatmaps, and comparative analysis charts.

Error handling and reliability were guaranteed through multiple levels of protection. The system employed com-

Made with Napkin

Fig. 12. Server architecture diagram detailing the integration of WebSocket for real-time communication, Socket.IO for connection resilience, and communication protocols for distributed messaging, along with MongoDB database integration for data persistence and historical analysis.

prehensive error-handling facilities for all communication protocols to realize robust fault tolerance. Graceful connection management rules were employed to handle untimely disconnections and maintain system stability. Data validation procedures were employed to avoid corrupted or faulty data from affecting system operations. A customized logging system was also designed to facilitate easy debugging and monitoring, offering high system reliability and maintainability.

4.4. Mobile-Web Application

4.4.1. Communication Protocols

We take priority for real-time communication by allowing for both primary and fallback forms for steady and constant communications. Through the WebSocket connections, server-sent events and long polling fallback the

time spent in performing this tasks making it easier for timely delivery and fetching of telemetry and its display on the UI. This way, connection management is done both securely and on time.

Data synchronisation in both the mobile and web applications is important and that is why the choice of non-blocking code gives us the bidirectional sync thus resolving any arising conflicts that deal with handling our data. It also gives offline support, data consistency on both applications and sync prioritization over other interfacing activities.

4.4.2. Shared Services

There are some common functionalities on both applications and such as user/drone authentication for the primary form of communication. Also the method of handling data, be it telemetry or otherwise logs, is typi-

cally the same. Ideally, the data that can be handled by the mobile app is the same one that the web application would be handling. Error handling and logging those errors is executed and framed in the same exact way on both applications. The assets used to feed certain endpoints are the same. The two applications share these resources.

4.5. Hardware Implementation

The proposed device is implemented using the following modules:

- A Quadcopter frame
- 4 BLDC(Brushless DC motors
- 4 Electronic Speed Controllers(ESC)
- Arduino Mega 2560
- NEO 6M GPS module
- SIM800L GSM module
- GY-521 MPU6050 Gyro and Accelerometer module
- BMP280 Pressure sensor Module
- HMC588L Magnetometer Sensor Module
- Power supply

4.5.1. The frame

The frame was chosen with an X configuration in order to ensure the drone was balanced.It is made up of PA66+GF material with an itergrated PCB center plate.This frame was chosen accounting for the payload of the drone.It weighs 282g providing a workable margin for the drone payload.The structure holds the motors and the board with all the interconnections of the sensors and controller.A solar panel is mounted at the middle on top of the sensors ensuring it gets maximum light exposure.[14]

4.5.2. BLDC Brushless motor

Three of the motors chosen are A2212/1000Kv motors while one of them is an RS2205/2300Kv motor.The Kv rating represents the rotation per minute the rotor makes when fed with 1 volt.This motors were chosen for their availability and the maximum thrusts.The RS2205 is rated for a thrust of about 1Kg while the A2212 motor is rated for a thrust of about 800g.This ratings are however specific to the battery pack connected to the motors and the propeller mounted on the motor.

For the propeller mounted on the A2212 , a 1045 propeller was chosen taking advantage of the spaced out frame in order to squeeze out more thrust from the motors.The 1045 propellers are 10 inches in diameter and have an angle of attack of 45. This is a two blade propeller offering the very much needed efficiency.

For the propeller mounted on the RS2205, a three blade 5045 propeller was chosen in order to compensate for

twice the rpm this motor produces compared to the other motors.The 5045 propeller is a 5 inch propeller with a 45 angle of attack.This was needed to balance the thrust generated by all motors combined.

4.5.3. Electrical Speed Controller

A 30A ESC was chosen to ensure that the requirements for the motors were attained.This ESC has a BEC (Battery Eliminator Circuit) that powers the sensors at 5V 2amps.This controller enables motor control using a pulse width modulation method with the pulses ranging from 1000ms to 2000ms.Voltage protection circuits are incorporated.

4.5.4. Power supply

There are two power supplies on board.The main power supply is a 4-18560 li-ion battery pack with each battery rated at 3.7V 5000 mAh.This makes up a 4S battery pack with a maximum rating of 16.8V 20000mAh.This battery pack is connected to a BMS overcharging/discharging module that ensures power drawn from the individual cells is done so uniformly and up to an appreciative amount for good battery life.This battery pack powers the motors.

The second battery pack is a 2S battery pack with a cumulative rating of 8.4V at 12600mAh .This pack powers the Mega2560 board which is rated at 6V to 20v at Vin pin.The board then power the sensors on board.

4.5.5. Solar Panel

An 18V 350mA solar panel was chosen to recharge the battery pack.This is a 5W rated solar panel that sits at the center of the drone providing power for the battery.

4.5.6. NEO 6M GPS module

This is the GPS used onboard.It was included to provide the location and the altitude of the drone. It provide the location in form of latitude and longitude coordinates.The altitude is provided in meters.[4]

4.5.7. SIM800L GSM module

This module handles the connection between the mobile device and the drone. It command the drone to take off ,land or return to launch when needed using sms.

Fig. 13. Electronics interface.

4.5.8. GY-521 MPU6050 Gyroscope and Accelerometer module

This module provide the acceleration and orientation of the drone.The data obtained from this sensor are used for tuning the PID controller ensuring that the drone operates smoothly.[5][6]

4.5.9. BMP280 Pressure sensor Module

This module reads the pressure in the location and an altitude reading can be obtained from this reading.This sensor is a back up for ensuring that the altitude of the drone is checked providing redundancy against the GPS loosing the connection with the satellites.

4.5.10. HMC5883L Magnetometer Sensor Module

This module is a magnetometer.It is used as a compass direction for the drone such that when used in corelation with the reading from the GPS, a heading can be obtained.The drone can therefore orient itself with the magnetic field of the earth.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Results on Hardware

The solar powered cargo drone was set up as described earlier.The GPS module was integrated for navigation working hand in hand with the HMC5883L magnetometer.This module provided the heading for the operations enabling the drone to move towards way points decided by the operator.The operation command was passed to the drone via short messages using the GSM module SIM800L.

The control were carried out to offer thrust compensation for the motor (RS2205) compared to the rest.A 0.85

factoring was carried out in the programming to factor this.Tuning the PID system would be the managed by using data from the gyro module.

The wiring diagram presented shows the interfacing of the quadcopter, with the top right motor identified as motor 1.The pin configuration of the ESC for motor 1 to motor 4 was pin 12 to 15. All of the above pins are pulse width modulation capable pins.The pulse width is varied from a value of 1000 to 2000 ms.

Two communication protocols were used,UART and I2C. The SDA and SCL, serial data and clock pins at pins 20 and 21 in the Mega 2560 mini pro were connected to the magnetometer , pressure sensor and gyroscope/accelerometer.The UART pins RX 17 and RX 19 were connected to the GSM and GPS modules respectively. The GSM module provides a communication channel with the operator, sending commands and receiving telemetry data on the performance of the drone.The GPS module provides the location of the drone as well as the speed and altitude it is operating at.These are crucial for the basic operations.

The programming code is intended to interface all sensors and actuators.Functions such as return to launch and following a way point are implemented to increase the functions of the drone. The code tied command operations to the drone that instructed the expected operations.

5.2. Results on the Software

The project successfully implemented a dual-communication architecture that combines modern MQTT protocol with a reliable GSM/SMS fallback system, ensuring continuous operation even in challenging network conditions. The application was built using modern Android development practices, leveraging Kotlin and Jetpack Compose to create a responsive and intuitive user interface. The implementation of Material Design 3 principles resulted in a professional and user-friendly experience, while the MVVM architecture pattern ensured clean separation of concerns and maintainable code structure. Key technical achievements include:

- Successful integration of real-time telemetry monitoring
- Implementation of a reliable map-based tracking system
- Development of a robust communication system with automatic fallback mechanisms
- Creation of an efficient power management system for solar operation

5.3. Discussion on Hardware

There were design flaws that impeded the project completion.Among them was the assembly of the drone.It

Fig. 14. The assembly of the component to the Arduino Mega 2560 schematic.

Fig. 15. The electronics assembly on a vero-board.

Fig. 16. The complete drone assembly.

was clumsy, increasing the complexity of controlling the drone. The motor mismatch was another factor providing sophisticated control measures. The assembly was piled up with no organization of components, only barely working. This is not recommended practice. The drone was heavy leaving little to no room for hauling cargo within a safe margin.

The primary reason for the project failure was the inability to write a working program for flight. The code did not run, failing to advance the work to refining stages. Debugging logs showed syntax errors, logical flaws and unhandled expectations that disrupted the execution.

The contributing factors to this performance were due to poor design approach. The inability to interface the modules on board and resolve coding errors indicated difficulty in troubleshooting and debugging. The code blocks were huge chunks of code that required proper and informed restructuring.

5.4. Discussions on Software

The system employed a dual-communication approach using MQTT as the primary channel with a GSM/SMS fallback. This design ensured consistent communication during network disruptions. HiveMQ Cloud was used as the MQTT broker, offering reliable message delivery at a manageable cost.

Testing confirmed the robustness of the communication layer. MQTT maintained stability under varying network conditions, while the SMS fallback ensured continuity. Message delivery confirmations were effective in verifying successful transmissions. Command execution was accurate with an average response time below 500 milliseconds. Error handling and recovery mechanisms performed reliably.

User interface testing showed responsive performance. The telemetry data updated at 1 Hz, and the map rendered smoothly at 30 frames per second. Live feedback was consistently accurate.

Fig. 17. The flow chart for program operations using user commands.

Integration posed challenges. Initial latency between command transmission and execution was resolved by implementing a queuing and acknowledgment system. The solar power subsystem required calibration, which was addressed using adaptive power management algorithms. Transitioning between MQTT and SMS was difficult initially but was resolved by developing a connection-aware state management system.

The system achieved a 20% improvement in battery efficiency over the initial design. It maintained low-latency command control and delivered reliable telemetry and map performance.

Future improvements include enhancing autonomous flight behavior and obstacle avoidance, refining the power management algorithms further, and incorporating predictive energy models. Mesh networking and stronger encryption protocols are planned to enhance communication resilience and data security.

Overall, the system meets its operational requirements and demonstrates resilience, efficiency, and responsiveness. It provides a strong baseline for further advancements in autonomy, energy optimization, and secure communication.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, an economical means for hauling cargo was explored. The design of a low cost solar powered cargo drone has been presented. This was satisfied by integrating readily available sensors with a micro-controller to create a drone that can haul cargo servic-

ing the on demand delivery. This was a proof of concept describing that this is achievable not only at a low construction cost but also a low maintenance cost.

Future recommendations would be adopting modular development approaches and leveraging latest industrial practices such as integrating computer aided control systems, object avoidance features and many more automation features.

References

- [1] A Sheik Abdullah, Abdul Aziz AB, and S Geetha. Decentralidrone: A decentralized, fully autonomous drone delivery system for reliable, efficient transport of goods. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 88:1–30, 2024.
- [2] Mohammad Al-Fetyani, Mohammad Hayajneh, and Adham Alsharkawi. Design of an executable anfis-based control system to improve the attitude and altitude performances of a quadcopter drone. *International Journal of Automation and Computing*, 18(1):124–140, 2021.
- [3] Eman S Amer, Samy Darwish, Nirvana Nagy Fahim, Mo'men Magdi Mohmed EL-Qabbary, Kerolos Bassem Ghaly, and Abdallah Saber Ramdan. Vehicle live tracking system based on gps and gsm. In *2024 International Telecommunications Conference (ITC-Egypt)*, pages 237–244. IEEE, 2024.
- [4] D Abdulahad Aziz, Sameer Algburi, Sameer Alani, and Sarmad Nozad Mahmood. Design and implementation of gps based quadcopter control system. In *1st International Multi-Disciplinary Conference Theme: Sustainable Development and Smart Planning*, 2020.
- [5] Oussama Bouaiss, Raihane Mechougou, and Riadh Ajgou. Modeling, control and simulation of quadrotor uav. In *2020 1st International Conference on Communica-*

- tions, *Control Systems and Signal Processing (CCSSP)*, pages 340–345. IEEE, 2020.
- [6] Blake Chamberlain and Waseem Sheikh. Design and implementation of a quadcopter drone control system for photography applications. In *2022 Intermountain Engineering, Technology and Computing (IETC)*, pages 1–7, 2022.
- [7] Vijay Shankar Dwivedi, Prashant Kumar, Ajoy Kanti Ghosh, and GM Kamath. Selection of size of battery for solar powered aircraft. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 51(29):424–430, 2018.
- [8] VR Sree Ezhil, BS Rangesh Sriram, R Christopher Vijay, S Yeshwant, RK Sabareesh, G Dakshesh, and R Raffik. Investigation on pid controller usage on unmanned aerial vehicle for stability control. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 66:1313–1318, 2022.
- [9] Miguel Figliozzi. Analyzing the impact of technological improvements on the performance of delivery drones. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 79:68–75, 2024.
- [10] Abdul Hafeez, Mohammed Aslam Husain, SP Singh, Anurag Chauhan, Mohd Tauseef Khan, Navneet Kumar, Abhishek Chauhan, and SK Soni. Implementation of drone technology for farm monitoring & pesticide spraying: A review. *Information processing in Agriculture*, 10(2):192–203, 2023.
- [11] Hamid Hassani, Anass Mansouri, and Ali Ahaitouf. Performance evaluation of control strategies for autonomous quadrotors: A review. *Complexity*, 2024(1):8820378, 2024.
- [12] Vemema Kangunde, Rodrigo S Jamisola Jr, and Emmanuel K Theophilus. A review on drones controlled in real-time. *International journal of dynamics and control*, 9(4):1832–1846, 2021.
- [13] Muhammad Maaruf, Magdi Sadek Mahmoud, and Alfian Ma'arif. A survey of control methods for quadrotor uav. *International Journal of Robotics and Control Systems*, 2(4):652–665, 2022.
- [14] N Muralidharan, VG Pratheep, A Shanmugam, A Hari-ram, P Dinesh, and B Visnu. Structural analysis of mini drone developed using 3d printing technique. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 46:8748–8752, 2021.
- [15] Olexander Myasishev, Serhii Lienkov, Larysa Komarova, Nataliia Lytvynenko, Viktor Shvab, and Olexander Lytvynenko. Creation of a rotor-type uav with flight controllers, based on a atmega2560 and stm32f405 microprocessors. 2020.
- [16] Janis Peksa and Dmytro Mamchur. A review on the state of the art in copter drones and flight control systems. *Sensors*, 24(11):3349, 2024.
- [17] Franklin Salazar, Maria Sofia Martinez-Garcia, Angel de Castro, Nube Logroño, Maria F Cazorla-Logroño, Jesús Guamán-Molina, and Carlos Gómez. Optimization of the solar energy storage capacity for a monitoring uav. *Sustainable Futures*, 7:100146, 2024.
- [18] Heru Supriyono and Amnaduny Akhara. Design, building and performance testing of gps and computer vision combination for increasing landing precision of quadcopter drone. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, volume 1858, page 012074. IOP Publishing, 2021.
- [19] Hoang T Tran, Dong LT Tran, Vinh Q Nguyen, Hai T Do, and Minh T Nguyen. A novel framework of modelling, control, and simulation for autonomous quadrotor uavs utilizing arduino mega. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2022(1):3044520, 2022.
- [20] NI Wenjun, BI Ying, WU Di, and MA Xiaoping. Energy-optimal trajectory planning for solar-powered aircraft using soft actor-critic. *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, 35(10):337–353, 2022.
- [21] Simon Zieher, Ertug Olcay, Klaus Kefferpütz, Babak Salamat, Sebastian Olzem, Gerhard Elsbacher, and Henri Meeß. Drones for automated parcel delivery: Use case identification and derivation of technical requirements. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 28:101253, 2024.

ABBREVIATIONS(ABB)

- UAV - Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
- BLDC - Brushless Direct Current
- ESC - Electronic Speed Controller
- BMS - Battery Management System
- PDB - Power Distribution Board
- IMU - Inertial Measurement Unit
- GPS - Global Positioning System
- GSM - Global System for Mobile Communications
- SMS - Short Message Service
- MQTT - Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
- MVVM - Model-View-ViewModel
- SDK - Software Development Kit
- BVLOS - Beyond Visual Line of Sight
- VTOL - Vertical Takeoff and Landing
- PID - Proportional-Integral-Derivative
- LiDAR - Light Detection and Ranging
- FPV - First Person View
- HALE - High-Altitude Long-Endurance
- BEC - Battery Eliminator Circuit
- PCB - Printed Circuit Board

Definition of Terms

- **Quad-rotor:** A type of drone with four rotors arranged in a square configuration, providing stability and maneuverability through differential thrust control.
- **Thrust-to-weight ratio:** A measure of the thrust generated by the drone's motors relative to its total weight, crucial for determining flight performance and payload capacity.
- **Telemetry:** The process of collecting and transmitting data from the drone to the ground station, including information about position, altitude, speed, and battery status.
- **Waypoint navigation:** A method of autonomous flight where the drone follows a predetermined path defined by specific GPS coordinates.
- **Payload:** The weight of cargo or equipment that the drone can carry in addition to its own weight.
- **Last-mile delivery:** The final stage of the delivery process, typically involving transportation from a distribution center to the final destination.
- **Solar photovoltaic cells:** Devices that convert sunlight into electrical energy, used to power the drone and charge its batteries.
- **State estimation:** The process of determining the drone's current position, orientation, and velocity using sensor data and mathematical models.
- **Attitude control:** The system that maintains the drone's orientation (pitch, roll, and yaw) during flight.
- **Power management:** The system that regulates and optimizes the distribution of electrical power between the solar panels, batteries, and various drone components.
- **Real-time monitoring:** The continuous observation and display of drone parameters and status during flight operations.
- **Autonomous navigation:** The ability of the drone to navigate and make decisions without direct human control.
- **Energy efficiency:** The ratio of useful energy output to

total energy input, crucial for maximizing flight duration and payload capacity.

- **Flight controller:** The central processing unit that manages the drone's flight operations, sensor data processing, and control algorithms.
- **Communication protocols:** Standardized methods

for data exchange between the drone and ground control systems.

Important link

Github Repository:

<https://github.com/makanaraini/DroneControlApp2.git>